

Balancing Conservation and Sustainable Development through Spatial Planning Zoning: Evidence from Sharri National Park, Kosovo

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Abstract: Spatial zoning is a key environmental management instrument for balancing biodiversity conservation with socio-economic development in protected areas. In Southeast Europe, national parks face increasing development pressure driven by tourism, private land ownership, and local economic expectations. This study examines the zoning revision of Sharri National Park (Kosovo), based on an integrated methodological framework combining ecological assessment, GIS-based analysis, and a structured expert-based multi-criteria evaluation approach. The analysis uses orthophotos (2024), cadastral data, satellite imagery, field verification, and 105 zoning-related requests. The evaluation integrates environmental, socio-economic, and planning criteria through qualitative expert judgment supported by spatial analysis. Results show that zoning functions as an adaptive governance tool: while the draft plan proposed a 75% reduction of development zones, 78.1% of requests were ultimately approved, reflecting the need to balance ecological priorities with development pressures. The study highlights the importance of transparent criteria, expert evaluation, and stakeholder participation for achieving socially acceptable and ecologically sound zoning outcomes.

Keywords: spatial zoning; protected areas; environmental management; sustainable development; national parks; Kosovo.

1 Introduction

Protected areas are central to biodiversity conservation but are increasingly shaped by competing socio-economic pressures (Dudley 2008). National parks must reconcile ecological protection with development needs, particularly under growing tourism and infrastructure expansion (Lockwood 2012). Spatial zoning provides a framework for managing this balance by allocating differentiated levels of protection and use (IUCN 2019, Eagles et al. 2002). However, its effectiveness depends not only on ecological criteria but also on governance quality, institutional coordination, and stakeholder participation (Borrini-Feyerabend et al. 2013). In transition contexts, zoning often reflects tensions between conservation and development.

Empirical studies on how zoning revisions are implemented in practice remain limited, particularly in post-socialist systems (Paloniemi et al. 2015, Hiedanpää

and Bromley 2016). This study analyses the zoning revision of Sharri National Park by examining the ecological verification of strictly protected zones, analysing the criteria-based evaluation of development zones, and assessing the role of expert judgment, GIS analysis, and public participation.

2 Study Area and Institutional Framework

Sharri National Park, located in southern Kosovo, covers approximately 53,281 ha and is classified as an IUCN Category II protected area (Figure 1). The park includes diverse ecosystems, from alpine zones to forested valleys, supporting high biodiversity and key species such as the Balkan lynx and brown bear. At the same time, the park is a socio-ecological system with settlements, traditional land use, and growing tourism development, particularly in Brezovica, Prevallë, and Guri i Dellocit. These dynamics create strong pressures on land use and zoning decisions.

The existing zoning system (2013) includes three zones: strict protection (Zone I), active management (Zone II), and sustainable development (Zone III). Over time, this structure became misaligned with ecological knowledge and development pressures, prompting revision.

Figure 1. The territory of the "Sharri" National Park.

3 Materials and methods

This study applies an integrated framework combining ecological assessment with a structured expert-based multi-criteria evaluation approach (Lockwood et al. 2012, Malczewski 1999, Hiedanpää and Bromley 2016). The

methodology consists of two main components, namely the ecological verification of strictly protected zones (Zone I) and the qualitative multi-criteria evaluation of development requests (Zone III).

Data sources include orthophotos from 2024, cadastral data, satellite imagery, field verification, and a total of 105 public requests. The unit of analysis is the individual zoning request, defined as a parcel or polygon. Each request was systematically recorded, spatially analysed using GIS tools, evaluated against a defined set of criteria, and subsequently reviewed by a multidisciplinary expert group.

3.1 Criteria Framework

The evaluation framework is based on three main groups of criteria, encompassing environmental, socio-economic, and planning/legal aspects. Environmental criteria include biodiversity, ecological connectivity, terrain sensitivity, and proximity to water bodies. Socio-economic criteria address development potential, community needs, property rights, and tourism-related considerations. Planning and legal criteria focus on spatial coherence, infrastructure availability, and compliance with the existing planning framework.

In addition, several spatial criteria are incorporated into the analysis, including slope limitations, proximity to infrastructure, cadastral structure, and the application of buffer zones.

3.2 Decision Logic

The decision-making process follows a qualitative, expert-based approach without the use of numerical scoring.

Instead, decisions are derived from the degree of compliance with the defined criteria, supported by GIS-based spatial analysis, field verification, and consistency with planning regulations. Final outcomes are established through collective expert judgment.

3.3 Public Participation

A total of 105 requests were analysed, reflecting stakeholder interests and pressures, which were systematically integrated into the evaluation process. This structured approach contributes to ensuring transparency and consistency in decision-making.

4 Results

4.1 Redefinition of Strict Protection Zones (Zone I)

The scientific verification and revision of strictly protected zones resulted in a more ecologically coherent spatial configuration. The process involved the reassessment of biodiversity value, habitat integrity, and ecological connectivity, supported by field verification and spatial analysis.

Areas characterised by lower ecological value or anthropogenic disturbance were excluded from strict protection, while ecologically important zones were consolidated to enhance continuity and reduce fragmentation (Figure 2). This resulted in a more functionally effective protection regime aligned with current ecological conditions.

4.2 Draft Spatial Plan Zoning Proposal

The Draft Spatial Plan proposed significant changes to the zoning structure (Table 2), particularly a substantial

Figure 2. The territory of the "Sharri" National Park.

reduction of sustainable development zones (Zone III). The proposed configuration reduced Zone III by approximately 75%, transferring large areas into Zone II (active management and higher protection).

This proposal reflected a precautionary approach prioritising ecological protection. However, it also introduced strong constraints on development opportunities, particularly affecting privately owned land.

Table 1. Proposed zoning configuration under the Draft Spatial Plan.

Zone	Area (ha)	Share (%)	Change (ha)	Change (%)
Zone I	8,745.68	16.42	-627.12	-1.18
Zone II	43,573.71	81.80	+3,447.37	+6.47
Zone III	951.82	1.79	-2,820.25	-5.29
Total	53,271.21	100.00	0.00	0.00

4.3 Analysis of Zoning Requests

A total of 105 zoning-related requests were submitted during the public consultation process, representing a diverse range of stakeholders, including individual landowners, local communities, and private investors.

4.4 Typology of Requests

The requests can be broadly categorised into four main groups, reflecting different types of stakeholder interests and development pressures. The first and dominant category consists of requests for zoning changes from Zone II to Zone III, indicating a strong demand for expanded development opportunities, particularly in tourism-related areas.

The second category includes requests for the relaxation of construction conditions, primarily aimed at modifying restrictive planning regulations such as minimum parcel size and building coefficients. The third group comprises requests for infrastructure development, highlighting the need for improvements in road access, water supply, and energy infrastructure to support future development. Finally, a distinct category is formed by requests submitted by business actors and investors, which typically involve proposals for larger-scale tourism and development projects.

This classification indicates that zoning is not only a technical process but also a reflection of socio-economic pressures and development expectations.

4.5 Spatial Distribution of Development Pressure

The analysis reveals a clear spatial concentration of development pressure in specific areas, particularly in Brezovica (Štrpce Municipality), Prevalë (Prizren Municipality), and Guri i Dellocit (Suharekë Municipality). These locations function as “development hotspots”, characterised by high tourism potential and strong demand for land-use change. The concentration of requests in these areas suggests that zoning conflicts are spatially uneven and strongly linked to economic attractiveness and accessibility.

4.6 Final Zoning Decisions

Following the evaluation process, final zoning decisions reflect a compromise between ecological protection and development needs in Table 2.

Table 2. Statistical summary of final zoning decisions.

Decision category	Number of requests	Share (%)
Approved in Zone III	82	78.10
Retained in Zone II	5	4.76
Partially approved	7	6.67
Not related to zoning	12	10.47
Total	105	100.00

These results indicate a significant shift from the initial draft proposal towards a more flexible and socially responsive zoning framework.

4.7 Analytical Interpretation of results

The high approval rate (78.1%) suggests that development pressure played a decisive role in shaping final zoning outcomes. This indicates that, in practice, zoning decisions are not determined solely by ecological criteria, but also by socio-economic considerations and stakeholder influence. At the same time, the retention of a smaller proportion of requests within Zone II demonstrates that ecological constraints were still applied in cases of high environmental sensitivity. This balance reflects a hybrid decision-making model, where environmental protection and development needs are negotiated rather than strictly prioritised.

5 Discussion

5.1 Zoning as a Negotiated Governance Process

The case of Sharri National Park demonstrates that spatial zoning functions not only as a technical planning tool but also as a negotiated governance mechanism. The integration of expert-based evaluation, spatial analysis, and public participation highlights the complex interaction between scientific assessment and social legitimacy. The findings confirm that zoning effectiveness depends less on rigid technical criteria and more on the ability to balance competing interests through transparent and adaptive decision-making processes (Borrini-Feyerabend et al. 2013, Paloniemi et al. 2015).

5.2 Balancing Ecological Protection and Development Pressure

The contrast between the initial draft proposal and the final zoning outcomes illustrates the dynamic nature of zoning. While the draft plan prioritised ecological protection through a significant reduction of development zones, the final decisions reflect a more balanced approach influenced by stakeholder input. This suggests that strict conservation-oriented zoning may face resistance if it does not adequately consider socio-economic realities. Conversely, incorporating stakeholder perspectives can improve the social acceptability and implementability of spatial plans.

5.3 Role of Expert-Based Multi-Criteria Evaluation

The study demonstrates that a structured expert-based multi-criteria evaluation framework can provide a flexible and context-sensitive alternative to formal quantitative MCDA approaches.

By integrating ecological, socio-economic, and planning criteria without rigid scoring, the process allows for context-specific interpretation of criteria, the incorporation of local knowledge, and adaptive decision-making. However, this approach also introduces a degree of subjectivity, which must be managed through transparency and institutional accountability.

5.4 Limitations of the Study

Despite its comprehensive approach, the study has several limitations. First, the lack of a quantitative scoring system, due to the absence of a formal MCDA framework, limits the reproducibility and comparability of the results. Second, the decision-making process relies heavily on expert judgment, which may introduce a degree of subjectivity and potential bias.

Third, the temporal limitations of ecological data must be considered, as field verification reflects conditions at a specific point in time and may not capture long-term ecological dynamics. Finally, the uneven availability of socio-economic data, particularly at the local level, constrains a more detailed assessment of economic impacts and demographic trends. These limitations highlight the need for future research to integrate more systematic evaluation methods and longitudinal data.

5.5 Implications for Spatial Planning and Policy

The findings provide important insights for spatial planning in protected areas. In particular, zoning should be understood as a dynamic and adaptive process rather than a fixed regulatory framework. Furthermore, the use of clear and transparent criteria is essential for ensuring legitimacy in decision-making processes. Public participation also plays a critical role in balancing competing interests, while hybrid approaches that combine expert knowledge with stakeholder input appear to be particularly relevant in transition contexts.

6 Conclusions and Policy Implications

This study demonstrates that spatial zoning, when applied as an adaptive and evidence-based instrument, can reconcile conservation objectives with sustainable development needs in protected areas undergoing socio-economic transition.

The case of Sharri National Park shows that zoning is most effective when based on a structured criteria framework, that expert-based evaluation can support complex decision-making in data-limited contexts, and that stakeholder participation is essential for achieving socially acceptable outcomes. At the same time, the study highlights the importance of strengthening methodological transparency and analytical rigor in zoning processes. Future research should therefore focus on integrating quantitative multi-criteria methods,

monitoring long-term ecological and socio-economic impacts, and conducting comparative analyses across protected areas.

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